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PHYTOREMEDIATION OF GROUNDWATER HARDNESS USING *Camellia sinensis* IN A HYDROPONIC SYSTEM

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Groundwater hardness, primarily caused by elevated concentrations of calcium (Ca²⁺) and magnesium (Mg²⁺), poses significant challenges to water quality and palatability. This study investigates the efficacy of *Camellia sinensis* (tea plant) for the phytoremediation of hardness ions from groundwater using a hydroponic system. Over a 16-day experimental period, the removal efficiency of Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ was evaluated using single-plant and four-plant configurations, with control setups to account for abiotic adsorption by the coconut coir growth medium. The concentrations of Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ in water samples were monitored using atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS). For tissue analysis, plant samples were digested with concentrated nitric acid (HNO₃) prior to AAS, confirming bioaccumulation. A clear plant density-dependent removal efficiency was observed, with the four-plant system demonstrating optimal performance, achieving a 72% reduction in Ca²⁺ (from 45.35 mg/L to 12.8 mg/L) and a 56% reduction in Mg²⁺ (from 74 mg/L to 33.6 mg/L). Tissue-specific accumulation revealed Mg²⁺ was predominantly stored in leaves, whereas Ca²⁺ uptake exhibited signs of physiological regulation and translocation constraints. An observed decline in Mg²⁺ accumulation efficiency at higher external concentrations, despite an absence of visible phytotoxicity, indicates a defined operational threshold for the system, with the effects of extreme hardness remaining uncharacterized. The system-maintained pH stability within acceptable drinking water standards (7.6–8.1). These results confirm the active uptake of hardness ions by *Camellia sinensis* and underscore the critical influence of plant density. While promising, the observed physiological limitations indicate the need for optimized loading rates, establishing this method as a potentially sustainable and scalable plant-based strategy for decentralized groundwater softening.

Keywords: Phytoremediation, Water hardness, Hydroponics, Groundwater treatment